

Determination of ethanol content in Sri Lankan marketed preparations of “*Nimba Arishta*” using Gas Chromatography – Flame Ionization Detection

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Ayurvedic medicinal products containing natural ingredients are widely perceived by the public as safer and more effective alternatives to synthetic chemical-based formulations due to their lower risk of adverse side effects. Among these, *Arishta* are widely utilized fermented Ayurvedic formulations available in the Sri Lankan market. The ethanol content of these formulations must be carefully monitored because it greatly affects the absorption and effectiveness of these products. It is important to ensure that consumers receive authentic and high-quality formulations to maintain trust in Ayurvedic medicine. The objective of the present study was to assess the ethanol content of some samples of ‘*Nimba arishta*’ available in a range of brands in the Sri Lankan market. In this study, samples from six different local manufacturers as over-the-counter products were obtained. Their ethanol contents were determined using a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID). 1% (v/v) acetonitrile was used as the internal standard and the sample solutions were directly injected. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way ANOVA with 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$) followed by Tukey's test. According to results, a maximum ethanol content of $10.4 \pm 0.141\%$ v/v and a minimum of $7.65 \pm 0.07\%$ v/v were detected across the samples. Statistically significant differences were observed in the ethanol content of the same *Arishta* formulation from different brands highlighting inconsistencies in the manufacturing or formulation practices. The lack of established guidelines for monitoring ethanol content not only raises concerns about therapeutic effectiveness but also potential risks associated with long-term use. These findings underscore the urgent need for standardized methods and regulatory mechanisms to ensure the quality, safety, and efficacy of Ayurvedic products in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Ayurveda, fermented preparations, GC-FID, polyherbal formulations, standardization*

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